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ACCORDINGLY, THEY BEAR BOTH ETHICAL AND LEGAL ACCOUNTABILITY”**

SENTIMENT ANALYSIS PERFORMANCE OF LORA-ENHANCED LLM'S

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ABSTRACT

On social media platforms, the increase in the number of users and the resulting increase in the data produced by users have accelerated the prominence of some technologies. The most well-known of these areas is Natural Language Processing (NLP), where sentiment analysis of user content is performed. Sentiment analysis is mostly applied to short texts. In this study, experimental comparisons of large language models (LLMs), known deep learning and machine learning algorithms are made using a dataset containing content from Twitter (X) users. In addition to this comparison, the LoRA (Low-Rank Adaption) strategy was applied to the DistilBERT model, one of the transformer-based large language models that forms the basis of the study, and the success of this fine-tuning method, which is lower cost and parameter efficient, was demonstrated. 8 different algorithms were included in the study: Machine Learning algorithms (Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest, XGBoost), Deep Learning Algorithms (Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)) and Transformer-Based Algorithms (DistilBERT and DistilBERT fine-tuned with LoRA). According to the results obtained, the LoRA-supported DistilBERT algorithm was the highest-performing algorithm with 82.38% accuracy. The results show that transformer-based architectures are much more efficient than classical deep learning and machine learning algorithms, especially in textual classification processes, when supported by new methods and strategies that increase efficiency in terms of fine-tuning, such as LoRA. It is anticipated that this study will be an important guide in applications such as sentiment analysis, where model selection is important.

Keywords: LoRA, LLM, Sentiment Analysis

LORA DESTEKLİ LLM'LERİN DUYGU ANALİZİ PERFORMANSI

ÖZET

Sosyal medya platformlarında kullanıcı sayısının artması ve bunun sonucunda kullanıcılar tarafından üretilen verinin artması bazı teknolojilerin ön plana çıkmasını hızlandırmıştır. Bu alanlardan en bilineni, kullanıcı içeriklerinin duygu analizinin yapıldığı Doğal Dil İşleme (NLP)'dir. Duygu analizi çoğunlukla kısa metinlere uygulanır. Bu çalışmada, Twitter (X) kullanıcılarına ait içerikleri içeren bir veri seti kullanılarak büyük dil modelleri (LLM), bilinen derin öğrenme ve makine öğrenmesi algoritmalarının deneysel karşılaştırmaları yapılmıştır. Bu karşılaştırmaya ek olarak, çalışmanın temelini oluşturan dönüştürücü tabanlı büyük dil modellerinden biri olan DistilBERT modeline LoRA (Low-Rank Adaption) stratejisi uygulanmış ve daha düşük maliyetli ve parametre açısından verimli olan bu ince ayar yönteminin başarısı gösterilmiştir. Çalışmada 8 farklı algoritma yer almıştır: Makine Öğrenmesi algoritmaları (Lojistik Regresyon, Destek Vektör Makineleri (SVM), Rastgele Orman, XGBoost), Derin Öğrenme Algoritmaları (Evrimsel Sinir Ağı (CNN), Uzun Kısa Süreli Bellek (LSTM)) ve Dönüştürücü Tabanlı Algoritmalar (DistilBERT ve LoRA ile ince ayarlanmış DistilBERT). Elde edilen sonuçlara göre, LoRA destekli DistilBERT algoritması %82,38 doğrulukla en yüksek performansı gösteren algoritma olmuştur. Sonuçlar, dönüştürücü tabanlı mimarilerin LoRA gibi ince ayar açısından verimliliği artıran yeni yöntem ve

stratejilerle desteklendiğinde, özellikle metinsel sınıflandırma süreçlerinde, klasik derin öğrenme ve makine öğrenmesi algoritmalarına göre çok daha verimli olduğunu göstermektedir. Model seçiminin önemli olduğu duygu analizi gibi uygulamalarda bu çalışmanın önemli bir yol gösterici olacağı öngörülmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: LoRA, LLM, Duygu Analizi

1. INTRODUCTION

With the use of social media, all communication dynamics have also undergone a series of transformations. This transformation has affected many areas such as health, marketing, politics, and media, and its sphere of influence is gradually expanding. Social media has continued to diversify with new types over time. One of these is the Twitter (X) platform, which was launched in 2006 [1]. Twitter (X), which emerged as a platform that allowed users to share their ideas as comments through short messages called tweets, has become a source of real-time information transfer about all kinds of social events taking place around the world over the years [2]. The increasing number of users on the Twitter (X) platform over the years and the demographic structure of these users, the wide age range of users, and the content with different views have attracted the attention of researchers. The researchers first started with analyses and concluded that the proportion of Twitter (X) users is young and that they mostly consist of urban users [3, 4].

Approximately 44% of users are “secret viewers”, that is, users who only watch content without actively sharing. As these analyses increase, researchers have begun to focus on the point that the analysis of users’ content should be focused on rather than user analysis [5, 6]. Figure 1 shows an example depiction of twitter (X) data.

Figure 1. Twitter (X) User Data

The Twitter (X) platform offers many opportunities in terms of data, but it also has difficulties in terms of sentiment analysis. For example, in awareness campaigns such as World Diabetes Day, users sharing beneficial information and experiences in terms of health can also affect the public's behavior in terms of health [7]. Twitter (X) is a platform that provides access to a large number of user data in events with great social impact such as this. However, it is useful to know the difficulties. Twitter (X), with its promise of very wide data access, has difficulties such as the limitations of the platform's API and difficulties in organizing the data, and therefore, very good analysis tools are needed to organize this data (including abbreviations, emojis and punctuation, grammar inconsistency, etc.) [8]. The current literature includes various machine learning applications for sentiment analysis, which is mostly done to understand the emotional state of users on Twitter (X) data [9]. These models, which also include hybrid methods, show quite good success even in understanding the complex emotional structures of users. So much so that this success even shows significant success in predicting the mental, health and mental states of users [10]. Later, research topics that go beyond sentiment analysis, such as why users use Twitter (X), why they interact with other accounts, and what the motivations are for this, have emerged [11]. Users follow brands and interact with them using methods such as comments and emojis. Businesses and analysts who use this interaction data can produce appropriate marketing strategies for the customer [12].

In summary, the transformation of social media has also increased user interactions. Platforms such as Twitter (X) in particular provide significant amounts of data for understanding, analyzing and providing feedback appropriate to user emotions.

In this study, a dataset consisting of user data obtained from Twitter (X) was used and the success of newly developed large language models (LLMs) in understanding the emotions of these users and the LoRA (Low Rank Adaption) method, which can achieve better results with more limited data and is parameter efficient, were compared with machine learning and deep learning methods.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sentiment analysis is a technology seen as a part of the natural language processing (NLP) process used to distinguish subjective information from the content in texts. In general terms, in sentiment analysis, the emotion expressed by the content of the data obtained from users is determined. These expressions are also shown in 3 main categories: positive, neutral and negative [13, 14]. The effects of sentiment analysis are seen in many areas such as social media, health services, political science, marketing techniques, where both the target audience is large and strategic decisions are important [15, 16].

Today, almost every institution or organization has a platform where customers can comment. Evaluating and analyzing the emotions of customers from the content of these institutions or organizations regarding their services and products is one of the basic applications of sentiment analysis. In recent studies, it has been reported that many useful inferences are obtained as a result of sentiment analysis from user content on social media platforms such as Twitter (X) and Facebook [14, 17, 18]. However, there are many difficulties that increase the complexity in the evaluation of these contents, such as the structure of each language being different and the emotional state being able to contain different contexts or the abbreviations used [19, 20]. All these difficulties can be solved by developing new methods. These solutions are possible with advanced machine learning algorithms that can perform more sensitive operations and have the ability to solve more complex problems [21, 22].

Another known application of sentiment analysis is Aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA). This method requires the identification of "aspects" in the text and the assignment of labels to the emotions in the determined aspects. In short, it can be called extracting emotions according to their directions [23, 24]. With this method, a more detailed understanding of user feedback is provided. KnowMIS-ABSA can be shown as an example of this application. In this study, how it will be applied and structured in various fields is explained with examples [23].

The development of technology brings with it new applications. In terms of sentiment analysis, the situation of only textual data being applied has begun to be overcome. In recent technologies, a multi-modal sentiment analysis system is being transitioned to, where video and image data are also taken into account. By combining features such as facial expressions and tone of voice in these images and videos with textual inferences, it becomes possible to obtain more precise and accurate results [25, 26].

Such developments suggest that the scope of sentiment analysis will expand in the future, and technologies that will enable richer emotional insights will come to the fore.

As a result, Large Language Models (LLMs) emerged as the most well-known tools in the development of sentiment analysis, which has many shortcomings, and they have improved their sentiment analysis capabilities. Very large text data was used to train these artificial intelligence tools, which have the ability to interpret and classify language with extraordinary accuracy. With the discovery of this ability, it was inevitable that it would spread to many areas such as consumer behavior, mental health, and social media analysis [27, 28, 29].

Stating that tools such as GPT have also demonstrated significant success in detecting nuanced psychological structures, Rathje et al. have shown that this technology can also be successfully applied to comprehensive datasets [30].

LLMs are increasingly used not only for simple sentiment analysis applications but also for challenging complex task-based and aspect-based sentiment analysis [31, 32]. As time goes by, the development of LLMs is also accelerating. As the latest developments, zero-shot and few-shot learning capabilities of LLMs have emerged. These methods reduce the need for labeled and comprehensive datasets and allow faster classification [33]. Such acceleration and development of needs are important for rapid analysis of public opinion and people's emotions during global and important events such as Covid19 [27, 34].

There are researchers, such as Hutson and Ratican, who suggest the unbiased text mining approach. This method offers a transformation and facilitation in terms of the creation of sentiment analysis methods. It is also among the conclusions of the study that this situation will increase the reliability of sentiment analysis [35].

As a result, sentiment analysis methods with LLMs have managed to reach a higher level in terms of both performance and reliability. Thanks to LLMs, both the performance in compatibility with different languages has been increased and the ability to learn from limited data has been improved. However, there are still aspects that need to be improved.

Today, the latest technology is the Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) method, which has been developed to fine-tune the parameters of LLMs and to obtain better results with more limited data. LoRA is the process of eliminating the inefficiency caused by revising all the parameters of the model by adding trainable low-rank matrices to the layers of the previously trained model [36, 37].

LoRA's performance can be integrated into complex architectures as well as single-task scenarios and works efficiently. Fujiwara et al. demonstrated its effectiveness by using this method on the Mistral large model [38]. Similarly, there are researchers such as Zeng et al. who have shown that it can be used for different tasks such as protein signal peptide prediction [39]. Valipour et al. expanded the traditional LoRA understanding and stated that they made the rankings dynamically during training with their method called DyLoRA and that LoRA can be adapted according to the needs [40]. This adaptability includes major improvements especially for mobile applications and real-time systems [41].

With the emergence of LoRA, it has assumed the role of a bridge that can also work in harmony with artificial intelligence applications thanks to its capabilities such as reducing costs, reducing analysis times, using fewer resources and high performance [42].

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1. Dataset

The dataset used in the study is the Sentiment140 dataset taken from the Kaggle database [43]. The dataset containing 1.6 million tweets collected from Twitter (X) is labeled as positive, negative and neutral. The Sentiment140 dataset, which has been made publicly available for sentiment analysis operations, has been sampled from 10 thousand tweets as positive, negative and neutral in order to make a balanced, efficient and healthy calculation. Afterwards, punctuation marks were removed and mentions and URLs were cleaned. Finally, the texts were converted to lowercase letters and preprocessed and made ready for processing. In addition, the AutoTokenizer operations of the HuggingFace [44] library and the Tokenizer operations of the TensorFlow [45] library were applied for deep learning and machine learning models.

3.2. Pre-processing

Before model training, the dataset was subjected to various preprocessing steps to make it ready for training. In addition to the preprocessing steps explained in the dataset section, TF-IDF vectorization and bigram features were used for machine learning algorithms, and pre-trained

tokenizers, primarily tokenizer, attention_mask and input_ids, were used for models such as DistilBERT, and the data was made more organized and appropriate. Figure 2 shows the preprocessing steps of the dataset containing 1.6 million tweets.

Figure 2. Data Preprocessing

3.3. Model Architectures

While making experimental comparisons; evaluations were made in 3 main model categories as traditional machine learning models, deep learning models and transformer-based models. In the machine learning category, SVM [46], Logistic Regression [47], XGBoost [48] and Random Forest [49] algorithms were implemented using XGBoost and Scikit-learn libraries. In the deep learning category, CNN [50] and LSTM [51] models were implemented with Sigmoid activation support in TensorFlow and Keras libraries.

In the transformer-based LLMs model category, the DistilBERT [52] model was used, which can be used both with full fine-tuning and the LoRA [53] method, which can be used using the PEFT library of the HuggingFace library.

3.3.1. Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression can be briefly said to be a statistical machine learning algorithm. The main and most important purpose of this algorithm, which is used for binary (two-class) classification problems, is to predict whether an observation belongs to a particular class.

Logistic regression, which can take numerical and categorical input values, returns values between 0 and 1 as output values. The general function of logistic regression given in Equation (1) is the w values weights, the x values features, and the b values bias value.

$$P(y = 1 / x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(wx+b)}} \quad (1)$$

The formula and graph of the sigmoid function of the logistic regression algorithm, which stands out with its features such as being simple, interpretable and fast, are given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Sigmoid Function

3.3.2. LLMs (Large Language Models)

LLMs are artificial intelligence models produced with a very large amount of data set for the purpose of better understanding, communicating and producing natural language.

It emerged as a result of training billions of data consisting of books, websites, articles and all kinds of writings. Basically, thanks to its extraction of statistical patterns of language, it has a structure that can summarize, translate and even respond to the text data it receives as input.

In this study, the DistilBERT method, which is a faster and smaller version of the BERT method, which is one of the LLM models, but has similar performance, was used.

BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) is a groundbreaking LLM method in the field of Natural Language Processing thanks to the association method it establishes between both the previous word and the next word of the input word.

DistilBERT is the version of the BERT method with the knowledge distillation technique applied during training. The basic equation of the knowledge distillation technique is given in equation (2).

$$L_{distill} = a \cdot L_{CE} + (1 - a) \cdot T^2 \cdot L_{KL} \quad (2)$$

- L_{CE} , represents the Cross Entropy loss where the DistilBERT model is compared with the true labels.

- L_{KL} , shows the Kullback-Leiber Divergence data between DistilBERT and BERT model outputs.

- T , represents the temperature hyperparameter used to smooth the outputs.

- a , represents the weighting states of the two losses.

The features of DistilBERT simplified from the BERT method are given in Table 1.

Table 1. BERT vs DistilBERT

Feature	DistilBERT	BERT
Speed	%60 (faster)	Normal
Performance	Retains %97	High
Layers (number of)	6	12
Parameters (number of)	66M	110M
Training (time)	%40 (shorter)	Long

3.3.3. LoRA-Enhanced LLMs

LoRA (Low-Rank Adaption) is a parameter fine-tuning technique that allows transformer-based models like DistilBERT or large language models to be trained with much fewer parameters than necessary.

In other words, when DistilBERT is combined with LoRA, it is trained by adding only small adaptation layers, namely LoRA layers, and the need to train the entire model is eliminated. In this way, the cost is reduced as much as possible and high-level success is achieved even in data with limited resources with less computation.

While all weights of the model are continuously updated in the traditional fine-tuning method, in the LoRA-supported fine-tuning method, the existing weights are frozen and the low-dimensional LoRA layers working with them are processed as seen in Equation (3).

$$w^l = w + \Delta w = w + A \cdot B \quad (3)$$

The w values specified in the equation show the original weight matrix that does not change, while A and B show the small-sized matrices learned by LoRA. Figure 4 shows that the incoming text data is first processed in the DistilBERT transformer-based model after parameter fine-tuning and generating low layers with LoRA.

Figure 4. LoRA-Enhanced DistilBERT

3.4. Training Strategy

To ensure a common standard for training and testing data, all models are divided into 80% training data and 20% testing data. For Transformer-based LLMs and deep learning algorithms, the batch size is 128 and the maximum sequence length is 50. All models are tested for an equal number of epochs. The LLM+LoRA model, which is the focus of the study, is optimized with reduced memory, reduced computational cost, and efficient fine-tuning features.

3.5. Evaluation Metrics

While evaluating the performance of the models, 4 main factors were taken into consideration. Priority was given to the accuracy value, then the precision, recall and f1_score factors were evaluated. While these calculations were made, metrics belonging to the scikit-learn library were used for classical models, while the compute_metrics calculation method, which is a special metric of the HuggingFace library, was used for transformer-based models.

3.5.1. Accuracy, Precision, Recall, f1_score

In this study, 4 basic metrics were used to evaluate the results, primarily accuracy, precision, recall and f1_score.

In order to understand these metrics well, the term confusion matrix must first be understood. Because these 4 metrics are based on this confusion matrix table. An example confusion matrix table is given in Figure 5.

#	Actual Positive	Actual Negative
Predicted Positive	✓ TP (True Positive)	✗ FP (False Positive)
Predicted Negative	✗ FN (False Negative)	✓ TN (True Negative)

Figure 5. Confusion Matrix

Accuracy: It is the name given to the value obtained by dividing the examples that the model predicted correctly by the total predictions. Equation (4) shows the equation for calculating the accuracy value.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (4)$$

In cases where the data is balanced, it is the most well-known evaluation metric used to measure overall success.

Precision: The estimated result of the model is an indication of how much of the data it predicted as positive actually is positive. Equation 5 shows the calculation equation of the precision value.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (5)$$

It is a measurement used to prevent false positives, such as spam filters in email systems not seeing real emails as spam.

Recall: It is a metric used to calculate how many true positives are predicted correctly, such as when the evaluation result of a cancer patient should not be negative. Equation (6) shows the calculation formula of the recall metric.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (6)$$

F1-Score: The f1-score metric, calculated by taking the harmonic average of the Precision and Recall metrics, provides a balanced measurement. Equation (7) shows the formula for calculating the f1-score value.

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (7)$$

It is an important metric for data where the data is unbalanced and the importance of precision and recall metrics increases.

4. RESULTS

The main focus of this study is to evaluate the performance increase that can occur when large language models (LLMs) are supported by a method such as LoRA, which can perform fine parameter tuning and increase model performance with less resource usage.

Table 2 presents the experimental results of the study. The 8 different models included in the study were evaluated with 4 different metrics, namely accuracy, precision, recall and f1_score.

Table 2. Comparison of models

#	precision	recall	f1-score	accuracy
Logistic Regression	0.7701	0.7708	0.7704	0.7640
Support Vector Machines	0.7458	0.7552	0.7505	0.7420
Random Forest	0.7403	0.7406	0.7405	0.7332
XGBoost	0.7114	0.7810	0.7446	0.7248
Convolutional Neural Network	0.7428	0.7251	0.7338	0.7297
Long Short-Term Memory	0.4863	1.0000	0.6543	0.5138
DistilBERT	0.8120	0.7961	0.8040	0.803
DistilBERT fine-tuned with LoRA	0.8314	0.8116	0.8214	0.8238

Among the evaluated models, the LoRA-supported DistilBERT model stood out with an accuracy value of 82.38%. DistilBERT, which reached an accuracy value of 80.3% without LoRA support, provided the second best performance.

On the other hand, when looking at traditional models, Logistic Regression provided the highest success with an accuracy value of 76.4%. Logistic Regression is followed by the SVM algorithm with an accuracy value of 74.2%.

Among the CNN and its algorithms that showed less success compared to other algorithms, CNN showed a moderate performance with an accuracy value of 72.97%, while LSTM exhibited the lowest performance with an accuracy value of 51.38%.

This result emphasizes the effectiveness of applying parameter-efficient fine-tuning methods such as LoRA on large language models (LLMs), especially in resource-constrained environments. The conclusion to be drawn from here is that LSTM becomes difficult to model effectively in short, noisy and informal texts such as tweets.

Figure 2 contains the visualization of the obtained results.

Figure 6. Accuracy comparisons of Models

To summarize, the LSTM, which provides the lowest performance, shows that it predominantly predicts a class when looking at the precision-recall analysis. This result indicates that the data

shows high recall-low precision in training and that more criteria should be evaluated without relying on accuracy alone.

In general, when the results are examined, LLM-based technologies have the potential to show high-level performance in sentiment analysis. The superior success shown by this model is not only based on accuracy, but also provides the opportunity to save resources and time when supported by methods such as LoRA.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, the role of large language models (LLMs) and especially their support with strategic methods such as LoRA in improving the prediction results in performing sentiment analysis on social media data is shown. The Sentiment140 dataset, which contains 1.6 million labeled user data, was used for sentiment analysis. In order to have a fairer scope of the evaluation, the dataset was processed with machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Logistic Regression (LG) and XGBoost, deep learning algorithms such as CNN and LSTM, and transformer-based methods such as DistilBERT and LoRA-supported DistilBERT. The LoRA model was specifically focused on due to its features such as reducing resource consumption, showing more success with a limited number of examples, and being able to perform efficient fine-tuning.

The obtained results clearly show that LLM-based models are significantly more successful than traditional machine learning methods and deep learning methods. Adding strategies such as LoRA to LLM methods increases success, and at the same time achieves this with less resource consumption and less cost.

In the study, 8 different models were evaluated and LoRA-supported DistilBERT (LLM) showed the best performance with an accuracy value of 82.38%. DistilBERT model ranked second with an accuracy value of 80.3%. The most successful algorithm among traditional methods was Logistic Regression with an accuracy value of 76.4%.

The findings obtained in this study emphasize the high potential of using effective techniques such as LoRA, which can show high success with limited resources and can perform parameter fine-tuning, with LLMs in order to achieve the desired success in environments where resources are insufficient. It also provides adaptable predictions in subjects such as the classification of short texts, where model selection is important.

It is envisaged that this study will form the basis for Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) applications that can be used in the analysis of low-resource areas and different, multilingual data sets, as well as to increase reliability.

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